

SUFFIXES FORMING PERSONAL NOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This article dealt with suffixes that form personal nouns in Uzbek and English languages. Moreover, the concept of “morphemics” was explained and ways of making new words in both languages were also mentioned. Suffixes in Uzbek and English languages were given with clear definitions and examples.

Key words: morphemics, morpheme, prefix, suffix, personal noun.

Vocabulary of any language is widened in two main ways: 1. To add suffixes to words in a language; 2. Adapted words from foreign languages. Both contribute to the enrichment of vocabulary of a language.

In Uzbek language there are two types of forming new words: the first one is affectation and the next one is composition. In the former way, we add some suffixes or prefixes to make new words. For example, we make a new word from a word base “qobiliyat” by adding the suffix “-li” meaning skillful in a sphere. qobiliyat(noun)+li=qobiliyatli (adjective). In the latter one we make new words by adding more than two words to one another. This creates compound words such as tosh(noun)+bag’ir(noun)=toshbag’ir(adjective), or sakkiz (number) +oyoq (noun) = sakkizoyoq(noun). In Uzbek linguistics a myriad of scientists have explored morphemics. D.Muhammadiyeva, D.Shodmonqulova, M.Hamroyev, X.G’ulomova, D.Muhammedova, Sh.Yo’ldosheva and so on did scientific works on this subject.

In English words are also made by suffixes or prefixes and another words to each other. For example, when we add suffix “-ment” to the verb “excite”, a new word “excitement” is made. Or we can create new compound words like “post+man=postman”, “grand+father=grandfather”, “air+plane=airplane”.

In Uzbek, morphemics (morpheme) (gr. morphe - shape) are often as suffixes. There are two types of suffixes according to their function: forming new words and changing shape of the word. Personal nouns, object nouns or place nouns can be made with the help of suffixes. Here we will talk about suffixes that form personal nouns in both Uzbek and English language.

In Uzbek, there are so many suffixes that form personal nouns.

➤ -chi - creates personal nouns from noun, adjective and number: “ish”(noun)+chi=ishchi(noun), “a’lo”(adjective)+chi=a’lochi(noun), “ikki” (number)+chi=ikkichi(noun).

➤ -dosh - makes new words that mean unity, companionship. For instance, vatandosh (“vatan”+dosh) means people who are from the same motherland or kasbdosh (“kasb”+dosh) represents people who do the same job and work at the same place.

- -shunos – often makes personal nouns which refer to people who work in a specific field: “til”+shunos=tilshunos (a person who works with linguistics), “siyosat”+shunos=siyosatshunos (a person who deals with politics).
- -paz – makes personal nouns who cook what the word base meant. For example, osh**paz** is a person who makes “osh”, or somsap**paz** is someone who cooks “somsa”.
- -bon – also makes nouns that refer to someone related to the word base like bog'**bon** is a person who works in a garden and takes care of plants, trees.
- -dor – forms nouns which means people who own things in the word base. For instance, pul**dor** (“pul” (word base)+dor(suffix)) possesses money.
- -xon – refers to someone who reads something: “gazet”+xon= gazet**xon** is someone who always reads newspaper.
- -furush – is a suffix that form personal nouns who sell something: “meva”+furush=mevafurush is a person who sells fruits; “chinni”+furush= chinnifurush is someone who sells plates; “paxta”+furush=paxtafurush refers to someone who sells cotton.
- -soz – words which mean the person who creates and fixes something are made with the help of -soz: “mashina”+soz=mashinasoz is a person who fixes cars; “soat”+soz=soatsoz is someone who creates and fixes watches, clocks.
- do'**z** – makes personal nouns who sew something. For example, do'ppido'**z** sews duppi; etikdo'**z** is a person who is busy with sewing boots.
- -gar – “savdo”+gar=savdogar; “zar”+gar=zargar; “kimyo”+gar=kimyogar. All of these mean people who work with what the word base meant “savdo”(trade), “zar”(jewelry) and so on.

In English language, there are also some suffixes (an affix which is placed after the stem of a word) that make nouns related to people's work and profession.

- -ist – a suffix of nouns, often corresponding to verbs ending in -ize or nouns ending in -ism, that denote a person who practices or is concerned with something, or holds certain principles, doctrines, etc:

Pianist, journalist, feminist, psychologist, machinist, novelist, realist.

- -er/or – sailor, visitor, conqueror, solicitor, inhibitor.
 - -ant/ent – student, president, resident, assistant, defendant, accountant.
 - -ee - is attached to verbs that take an object to form nouns with the meaning “the person who is the object of the action of the verb”:
- address + -ee =addressee (= the person whom someone else addresses),
referee, refugee, attendee.

- -ic/ician – indicating a person skilled or involved in a subject or activity: mathematician, politician, electrician, medic, paramedic, mechanic.

So all above mentioned are suffixes that form personal nouns in Uzbek and English languages. The main difference is that in Uzbek the number of suffixes is more than that in English. The suffix -er is equivalent of -chi in Uzbek as they both mean a person's work and profession. For example, in English “write+er=writer” and in Uzbek “yozuv+chi=yozuvchi” have the same function and meaning.

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